

BEFORE SCHOOL EDUCATION IN ORGANIZATIONS EDUCATION PROGRAMS WORK EXIT

M.E.Rustamova

Directors and specialists of pre-school educational organizations
Institute for training and improving their skills
Senior teacher of the "Methodology of preschool education" department
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8388575>

Abstract : The state curriculum of the "First Step" preschool education organization is a mandatory basic document for the creation of variable curricula. Educational organizations have the right to develop their preschool educational organization's working curriculum on the basis of the state curriculum of the preschool educational institution, depending on their territorial conditions, the personnel potential of the material and technical base of the preschool educational organization. have The working curriculum of the educational institution is drawn up by the pedagogues of the organization with the involvement of parents and approved in accordance with the current legislation.

Key words: variable, partial, complex, correctional programs, multidisciplinary specialized, inclusive education

Education and upbringing of children of preschool age is aimed at the comprehensive development of the child's social, emotional, cognitive and physical needs.

This will serve as a solid foundation for him throughout his life. Pedagogues of pre-school education organizations play an important role in the implementation of pre-school education goals. Therefore, it is important to provide them with ample opportunities to develop their skills and provide their services, and to support them.

The goal of the state policy in the field of preschool education is to realize the right of every child to quality and free education

Variability of modern system forms of preschool education in Uzbekistan, flexible attitude to the needs of society and individual, emergence of new types of preschool education for children are characterized by various pedagogical services. Among the factors affecting the effectiveness and quality of children's education in preschool education, the State requirements for the development of preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Improved state curriculum "Ilk Kadam" are important. These are considered as a guide for the creative activity of educators and determine the content of the educational process in preschool education. Reflecting the scientific and methodical understanding of preschool education, it contains content in all the main areas of child development.

A distinctive feature of modern preschool education in Uzbekistan is its variety, that is, various types of preschool education organizations, general type state and non-state preschool education organizations, multidisciplinary specialized preschool education organizations and joint-type pre-school education organizations, basic one-year educational groups, family-type groups in home conditions. Preschool education in Uzbekistan is distinguished by the variety of forms of providing preschool education services in the form of day and short-term groups. At the same time, despite the different types of education and the forms of services provided, they all have common goals and objectives.

of education content, forms and methods change can be entered in the part in Uzbekistan before school education in the field before school education services present reach types and of forms variability noted that it will be provided done. Education programs content and them done in raising variability each one before school education organization, even each one pedagogue own education programs to create and them done increase different methods use possible means. Variability main condition - "First step" of DOD main principles and requirements, as well as the State requirements, that is all before school education organizations of the child in development provide a must has been requirements compliance to do is a necessity.

Before school in education modern requirements of the pupil to the person directed education of the process content and organize to be done about new the concept determines. A new model for pedagogues of children development account received without before school education in organizations each one young groups for education programs work to exit possibility gives.

It is aimed to develop educational programs in order to organize educational processes in accordance with "State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age in the Republic of Uzbekistan", to create conditions for effective planning and management of the educational process of preschool children. according to

The contribution of each pedagogue to the implementation of the educational program is the basis for the assessment of his competence.

The educational program is a means of training and training of the pedagogue, and determines the direction of education.

In the development of educational programs in a preschool educational organization, the following tasks are expected to be implemented:

- creating favorable conditions for children, including children with special needs, to receive modern inclusive education based on an individual program;
- formation of children's feelings of love for the Motherland, respect for the family, national, historical, cultural values of their people, and the environment;
- formation of children's knowledge of different nations and traditions;
- formation of the child's personality, development of his creative ability;
- ensuring the social adaptation of the child and his readiness for primary education;
- introduction of modern educational programs and technologies into the educational process.

In all types of educational programs, the following activities are provided during the stay of children in preschool educational institutions:

- organization of children's activities in development centers;
 - activities in general groups;
- voluntary activities of pupils;
- organization of children's free time during the day.

The educational program of the preschool education organization was developed on the basis of the state curriculum "First Step", in which, as noted above, 80% of the programs have a mandatory comprehensive approach to five areas of child development and 20 percentage is formed by pedagogues of preschool education organization.

This part can be developed on the basis of any copyrighted programs (complex or partial) or on the basis of its own educational programs created in the course of educational activities of

a preschool educational organization. In addition, a preschool educational organization may implement educational programs protected by copyright that reflect the specific characteristics and system of a particular organization. For example, if the distribution of educational activities in the "First Step" state curriculum provides for 5 activities per day (children's activities carried out by the centers), then the preschool educational organization will provide 1 type of activity based on its direction. (activity in development centers) can form on a certain activity (environmental, physical, healthy lifestyle formation, artistic, aesthetic, etc.).

Thus, preschool educational organizations can use various partial and complex educational programs to develop their educational programs or include author's programs in their educational programs.

When developing a training program, most organizations tend to maintain the existing training program. Because this accumulated experience and the use of available resources will save the efforts of the administration and pedagogues.

If there is an opportunity to choose partial and comprehensive educational programs of preschool education, there will be an opportunity to enrich the activities of the preschool education organization, increase the efficiency and quality of the educational process.

How does the development of the educational program of a preschool educational organization take place? How to choose partial and comprehensive educational programs and include them in your educational program?

The technology of such a process includes three stages aimed at sequentially performing a number of tasks or actions:

Stage 1: analytical. The purpose of the stage is to identify the system elements of the work of the preschool educational organization that require updating and make it possible to create a basis for making a decision on the choice of comprehensive, alternative educational programs;

Step 2: Research. The purpose of the stage is to find and select partial and comprehensive programs that maximize the elimination of identified deficiencies in the activities of the preschool educational organization and direct its activities to effectively achieve state requirements and basic competencies;

Stage 3: Formative. In doing so, the working group forms its activities based on the Regulations, its task is to form an educational program based on the selected partial and comprehensive educational programs, as well as to prepare the text of the educational program and fill in a set of necessary documents.

The ongoing work on the creation of the educational program is concluded with discussion with all participants of the educational process and approval at the meeting of the Pedagogical Council. Then the team begins to implement the educational program.

MTT is recommended to select the programs used for the formation of its educational program based on the criteria of relevance, innovative potential, usefulness, reliability and perspective, as well as the compatibility of the programs with each other.

References:

1. Resolution No. 802 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 22, 2020 "On approval of the state standard of preschool education and upbringing".
2. Improved "Ilk Kadam" state curriculum for preschool educational organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2nd edition), 2022 .
3. Methodological advice on the use of the approximate basic educational program in the development of the preschool educational program in the educational organization. Institute of Educational Development of the Russian Federation .
https://firo.ranepa.ru/files/docs/do/metodicheskie_rekomendacii_po_iskolzovaniyu_primer_noy_osn_obrazov_prog_do.pdf
4. Say Ye.F., Grosheva IV, Nazarova VA, Ismailova MA State requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan and application of the state curriculum "Ilk Kadam". Methodical guide for trainers. Tashkent, 2019.
5. Grosheva IV, Mirziyoyeva Sh.Sh., Tashmuhamedova FB, Rustamova MZ, Development of educational programs in preschool educational organizations (Methodical guide) Tashkent, 2020